

THE STUDY OF PARASITIC NEMATODES OF VEGETABLES AND FRUIT CROPS IN DISTRICT MUSAKHAIL, BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

*In Pakistan, the nematode problems are rapidly increasing and widely damaging the host plants by various species of parasitic nematodes. There is a great need of investigation of occurrence, distribution, incidence and taking out taxonomic work. There is also need for evaluation of pathological impacts of the nematodes on crops yields. The present study was performed in the remote areas such as one of the most northern district Musakhail of Balochistan province, for nematodes populations associated with Fruits: Apple (*Malus pumila* Mill), Grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L), Water melon (*Citrullus lanatus*), Field crops: Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), Corn (*Zea mays*), Mung bean (*Vigna radiata*), Vegetables: Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L), Pepper (*capsicum annum*), Okra (*Abelmoscus esculentum*) and Brinjal (*Solanum melongena*) of ten (10) different sites of four (4) different localities during the study five (5) genera and seven (7) species of phytonematodes have been recorded and identified in September 2022. Among all nematode genera *Meloidogyne incognita* were most abundant in all the studied sites of district Musakhail. During the study occurrence frequency, distribution and incidence of parasitic nematodes were considered in ten equally sampled site. The genera *Meloidogyne* showed highest occurrence frequency and population densities while the genera *Hetrodera* showed the least occurrence frequency and population densities. The study showed the highest incidence at the Dakian site and least incidence was recorded at Zimriplasin site.*

Keywords: Parasitic Nematodes, Vegetables, Fruit, Crops, Musakhail, Balochistan

Introduction

Nematodes are small microscopic round worms that belong to the phylum Nematoda. They are abundant in earth crust, occur in various habitats (De Saliva *et al*, 2003). They reproduce the whole year and are greatly hazardous to plants in tropical areas of the world (brown,

1963). Most of the nematodes present in soil associated with plants and are considered as one of the most important pests of field crops and vegetables as well as fruit plants (Stirling *et al.*1998). Pakistan is located in Southern Asia, at the border of the Arabian Sea, India on the east, China in the north and Afghanistan and Iran on the west. Pakistan is located geographically at 30 00 N, 70 00 E. Fruits like mango, banana, apple, grape, Papaya, Pomegranate, Persimmon and different field crops as well as vegetables are produced in large quantity in Pakistan. Pakistan having more variety of ecosystems and rich in nematodes fauna that are adapted to various agro-climatic regions.

The occurrence and distribution of phytonematodes from various agricultural sites have been studied from Pakistan (khan *et al.* 2021). However, existence of phytonematodes in the soil of district Musakhail is relatively un-explored. In this regard, the study is formulated for the first time to carried out surveys study of phytonematodes identification, occurrence and population densities as well as incidence from the soil of district Musakhail as possessing suitable ecosystem, climate and host plants. District Musakhail is considered an agricultural district of province Balochistan, Pakistan due to natural appropriate climatic system. Musakhail district possesses a loamy fertile soil which can support a variety of vegetables, fruit and field crops. Here different crops, vegetables and fruit plants are widely grown that are greatly infested with phytonematodes. District Musakhail is mountainious and occupied by great biodiversity with latitude of 39.11 N as well as 21.05 E longitude.

District Musakhail is situated in northeast of the province on the border of provinces KPK and Punjab. The border districts of KPK and Punjab are Sherani and Dera Ghazi Khan respectively. Plant parasitic nematodes like cyst and lesion nematodes seriously damage the cereals crops especially wheat fields in the Sakarya provinces of Turkey. Thirteen (13) genera of plant parasitic nematodes damaging wheat fields in Turkey were isolated, identified and studied, (Kecici, *et al.*, 2022). Significance of hot water treatment against root-knot nematode, (*Meloidogyne incognita*) associated with tomato crops under poly houses conditions were studied by, (Gurjar, *et al.*, 2022). Eight (8) plant parasitic nematodes associated with *Crocus sativus L.* in Kishtwar district, Jammu and Kashmir, India, were recorded, (Thakur, *et al.*, 2021). Root-knot nematodes are the most dangerous plant parasitic nematodes associated with pomegranate and are widely spread throughout the Iran.

In (2015-2016) growth season, one hundred and ninety-five (195) soils and root samples were taken from major growing regions of pomegranate orchards (Khorasan Razavi, southern and Northern provinces) in the Eastern Iran. Several species of

Meloidogyne species were identified from all of the surveyed regions and identification of plant parasitic nematodes were carried out through molecular and morphological methods, (Katooli, *et al.*, 2021). *Meloidogyne* species are causing well known diseases and yield losses to vegetable crops. Effects of six (6) Iranian commercial fertilizers were used to control root-knot nematodes, were investigated in green houses as well as in laboratory, (Hemmatia and Saeedizadeh, *et al.*, 2020). Plant Parasitic nematodes cause great destruction to most of the cultivated crops in tropical as well as subtropical regions, (Sallam *et al.*, 2021; Fouda *et al.*, 2020). The signs of affected plants are mostly difficult to differ from other biotic and abiotic things due to their minute sizes, (Bogale, *et al.*, 2020). During detailed survey, 158 roots and soil samples of cucumber grown in forty (40) poly-houses, showing all samples root-knot nematodes, *Meloidogyne incognita* occurrence, were studied in at different locations of Rjastan, (Bhati, *et al.*, 2020).

A comprehensive study of occurrence, prevalence and severity of root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* species) associated with roots of major vegetables grown in Sudhnuti district of Azad Jammu and Kashmir was taken, (Tariq-Khan, *et al.*, 2020).

A survey of soil around the roots of fruit plants and vegetable crops infected by parasitic nematodes in Kashmir valley, Jammu & Kashmir was carried out to identify seven (7) new species and one (1) new record of given species *Helicotylenchus siddiqii* from soil around roots of *Glycine max L.* was recorded, (Handoo, *et al.*, 2020). A research study was conducted in the Pothowar areas of Pakistan on two temporally different fields of nematodes (*Tylenchulus semipenetrans*) infesting citrus plants. The research study clearly reported out that, densities of nematodes associated with citrus plants are much greater in the citrus orchards, where temperature is in the range of 26-29°C whole year while soil depth is of 30 cm and lower densities of citrus nematodes in the orchards, where temperature is in the range of 9-12°C whole year and soil depth of 45 cm. This research study also found out greater number of nematodes as well as root attached females in the months of April-June and August-September in the whole year. This work reported out population's differences in nematodes, associated with citrus plants, at different temperatures, soil depth and duration of time in the year, (Saeed *et al.*, 2019).

At different locations of Balochistan province of Pakistan, ten (10) species of nematodes associated with the roots of *Mentha spicata* while four (4) species of nematodes associated with the roots of *Mentha lognifolia* were recorded by, (khan *et al.*, 2019). During both growing seasons, a comprehensive survey of plant parasitic nematodes affecting

cucumber in green houses at four (4) different localities of district Semel in Iraq was carried out and highest incidence of root-knot nematodes was shown in autumn season, (Ami, *et al.*, 2018). Okra infested with *Meloidogyne incognita* in six (6) okra genotypes at naturally growing fields in district Layyah, Punjab, Pakistan were investigated and the suppression of *Meloidogyne* species by *Lecanicillium muscarium* were studied, (Hussain, *et al.*, 2018).

During the survey of maize fields, of eight (8) various locations in Balochistan province of Pakistan. Thirteen (13) plant parasitic nematodes was recorded. Of all seven (7) plant parasitic nematodes were reported in a single locality. Most of the *Pratylenchus zaeae* was found to be present in the maize fields, (khan *et al.*, 2019). Root-knot nematode (*Meloidogyne incognita*) species are the major threat for green house cultivations and cause great losses under protected plantation. Physical, Biological and organic amendments trials to control *Meloidogyne incognita* under protected cultivations were studied, (Bhati, *et al.*, 2021). Root-knot Nematodes prevalence, distributions as well as host ranges were investigated at Muzaffarabad and Pooch divisions of this region, (Tariq khan *et al.*, 2020; Tariq khan *et al.*, 2017).

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with walnut (*Juglans regia L.*) and almond (*Prunus dulcis Mill.*) were studied in most of the growing regions in Adiyaman province, Turkey and different species of nematodes associated with almond and walnut orchards were isolated and identified morphologically and systematically, (Tan, *et al.*, 2018). The responses of okra plants and chillies germplasm to root knot nematode especially (*Meloidogyne incognita*) in the green-houses were studied in Pakistan, (Ul-Haq, *et al.*, 2017). In Pakistan nineteen species that belongs genus *Aphelenchoides* and four species that belongs to genus *Aphelenchus* has been isolated and identified Recently, (Shahina *et al.*, 2019). Plant parasitic nematodes associated with roots of walnut trees (*Juglans regia L.*) in Hazara division, KPK, Pakistan were investigated and found *helicotylenchus* species the most abundant in Abbottabad and Mansehra along with some other plant parasitic species of nematodes, (Saeed, *et al.*, 2019).

Parasitic nematodes of plants cause infections to various varieties of commercially valuable plant crops families. Plant parasitic nematodes cause infections to many different crop plants but do not produce strong immune response, (Warmerdam *et al.*, 2018). Nematodes densities associated with different fruit plants at three different localities were investigated and twenty (20) species of plant parasitic nematodes were identified in Pishin district, Balochistan province of Pakistan, (Hussain, *et al.*, 2016). Seven (7) species of plant

parasitic nematodes associated with grapevine rootstock and seedlings in six (6) vineyards of two (2) districts of Baluchistan, Pakistan were observed and identified, (Khan, *et al.*, 2014). Estimated 80 billion US Dollars loss to global crops occur due to parasitic nematodes of crop plants Worldwide, (Jones *et al.*, 2013). Yield losses to a large number of different vegetables crops and fruit plants are due to parasitic nematodes of plants. Maximum number of orchards, agricultural, fields crops and fruit plants are infested by parasitic nematodes of plants, (Mittal and Goswami, 2005) Twelve (12) genera were recorded during a comprehensive survey associated with pomegranate in Kalat and Khuzdar districts of Balochistan, Pakistan, (Khan and Shaukat, *et al.*, 2010). Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* species) are widely spread throughout the world. *Meloidogyne* species infect a wide range of plant species of different kinds throughout the world, (Zarina and Shahina, 2010).

Materials and Methods

A survey was carried out during the season of crops in September, 2022 for the objective to isolate and identify the parasitic nematodes of plants attached with roots and found in the rhizosphere of fruit crops and vegetables as well as field crops from four (4) localities named, Toisar (sites: Tangsar, Zam, Zimriplasin and Toi) Drug (Sites: Kiwan and Tangisar) Musakhel (Sites: Chesanna and Dakian) Kingri (Sites: Rarahasham and khajori).

A total of 70 roots and soil samples of defected (20 fruit producing crops and 50 of vegetable plants,) was taken. The samples were kept in hygienic plastic zipped bags. Each sample was marked carefully maintaining respective information that is locality, time, host, and collection date. The soil samples were taken with the help of trowel of 25 cm length. The soil samples were taken to a depth of 20 cm and 10 cm (width) around each side of the plant. The samples were saved from direct sun rays. The samples were kept at 5-10°C. Parasitic Nematodes were separated from soil by applying (Cobb's, 1918) sieving and decanting technology and modified (Baermann, 1917) funnel technology. Plant parasitic nematodes of roots were isolated by using Stemerding's maceration filtration technology.

The roots of infected plants were directly observed under a stereo-microscope to detect and comprehend galls and other infected or injured parts by parasitic nematodes., (Aly khan and Juma khan Treen, 2012). The isolated parasitic nematodes were heated in microwave oven to kill them at (60°C), fixed in TAF (Tri-ethanol Amine Formalin), reacted with glycerin solution comprising bits of picric acid, Courtney, *et al.* (1955). For a period of about one week, nematodes were reacted with anhydrous glycerin, after this, nematodes

were mounted and identified following the principles made by Shahina *et al.* (2009); Mai and Lyon, (1975) And Siddiqi (2000).

Results and Discussion

All the ten sites were infected by phytonematodes. The five genera recorded were *Hetrodera*, *Meloidogyne*, *Aphelenchus*, *Helicotylenchus* and *Ditylenchus* extracted from field crops, vegetables and fruit plants at ten (10) sites of four different localities in district Musakhail, province Balochistan, Pakistan. The genus *Meloidogyne* was most abundantly distributed (10% occurrence frequency) throughout all the site studied except four sites followed by *Helicotylenchus* (7.14%) while genera *ditylenchus* as well as *Aphellenchus* were abundant in its distribution (5.71% occurrence frequency) and the genus *Hetrodera* was least in its distribution (table no.3 and 5). Dakian site was most affected by phytonematodes followed by the sites Chesenna and Khajori. The sites Tangisar and Zam were the least affected while Zimriplasin site was not affected by parasitic plant nematodes at all. (table no. 7). The plants with great density of parasitic nematodes were Okra, Mung bean and Pepper followed by Eggplant, Tomato, Water melon, apple and corn and the lest density of parasitic nematodes were recorded in Wheat and Grape. (table no. 4). The decreasing order of nematodes densities are as *Meloidogyne*, *ditylenchus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *Aphellenchus*, *Hetrodera*. Dakian site showed the greatest incidence as (71.42%) Zimriplasin the least as (0%) (table no. 7).

Owing to the privation of an inclusive survey of phytonematodes associated with field crops, vegetables and fruit plants in district Musakhail, such a comprehensive study is key to twitch working on a survey for the parasitic plant nematodes distributed in Musakhail district. The results of the study also deliver key information regarding phytonematode species associated with field crops, vegetables, fruit plants grown in district Musakhail, and conceivable potential of the phytonematodes for plants damages as well as fiscal impacts. This survey will help in formative of which phytonematodes are tangled in plant disease problems in Musakhail district. In addition, the study survey outcomes will help to indicate the importance of perfect nematode documentations while forecasting operative managing stratagem. Sami ullah and khanum (2022) conducted their research in district Bajaur, of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. They surveyed twelve localities of district Bajaur. They collected a total of two hundred samples of roots and soil of different vegetables and crop plants. They isolated and identified twenty-two species of nematodes. They recorded 18% of non-parasitic nematodes and 81% of plant parasitic nematodes. Saeed *et al.* (2022)

conducted a survey at different localities of district Sawat, KPK, Pakistan, to investigate the nematodes infecting persimmon (*Diospyros kaki, L.*) They collected soil samples around persimmon trees analyzed and identified nine (9) different species of nematodes from these samples.

They resulted *Helicotylenchus* species were more common in the samples collected. Zafar *et al.* (2022) conducted study of nematodes associated with *Malus pumila* to evaluate the management, control and identification of stylet bearing nematodes in Pakistan. They took soil samples from rhizosphere areas around infected *Malus pumila* plants and identified ten (10) species of nematodes from different localities of Pakistan. Malik *et al.* (2022) resulted that plant pathogenic nematodes cause great losses to viticulture.

They reported major nematodes infesting grapevines as *Meloidogyne, Pratylenchus, Tylenchus* and *Cricconimella* species. They also reported *Paralongidorus, Logidorus* and *Xiphinema* species acting as vectors for viruses that cause diseases in grapevines. Sikandar *et al.* (2021) performed their research over maize plants in Punjab regions of Pakistan to study the free living nematodes found in the rhizosphere. The research verified that plants productivity can be influenced by these nematodes. They also recorded destruction of the minerals in the roots of plants as well as at cellular and subcellular level. In this research, they recorded 24 species of free living as well as plants parasitic nematodes. They also reported that most of the portions of maize crops are affected due to the free living nematodes 65% while 35% was affected due to parasitic nematodes of maize plants. They reported that about 55% maize plants were affected by *Heterodera zaeae*. They also recorded that parasitic nematodes were found to make communities in the roots of maize plants.

Ali *et al.* (2021) performed a research survey in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to investigate the effects, incidence, occurrence and severity of *Meloidogyne incognita* that were infecting brinjal/eggplant (*Solanum melongena*). They also investigated the resistance caused by eggplant varieties to root-knot nematodes. They resulted that *Meloidogyne incognita* was the most frequent species that was followed by *Meloidogyne javanica* in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. They found that *Meloidogyne incognita* and *Meloidogyne javanica* were causing disease incidence in the range of 24-72% and the fields of Peshawar district were hotspot for root-knot nematode reproduction as well as 72% disease incidence. Khan *et al.* (2021) conducted extensive surveys of four different site of Lakki Marwat, KPK, Pakistan, from October 2019 to February 2020 and collected seventy-three (73) soil samples from rhizosphere areas of different crops, vegetables, fruit plants, medicinal plants, commercially

valuable trees, ornamental plants and subsequently investigated the presence of endopathogenic nematodes. They identified one genera only with two isolates as *Steinernema balochiense* (24) and *Steinernema siamkayai* (24%) while four (4) species of *Steinernema* (52%) were not identified.

Khan *et al.* (2021) studied, isolated and identified plant parasitic nematodes associated with *Coriandrum sativum L.* from ten (10) different locations of Balochistan, Pakistan. They resulted *Meloidogyne incognita* the most common species in the surveyed areas. They also tested mustard oils and castor oils and carbofuran (chemical) over larvae of *Hoplolaimus Columbus* and *Meloidogyne incognita* and resulted mustard oil most effective in controlling plant parasitic nematodes of *Coriandrum sativum L.* Jabbar *et al.* (2020) Surveyed different fields of rice in Faisalabad and Chiniot districts of Central Punjab, Pakistan, to investigate the incidence and prevalence of *Meloidogyne graminicola* infecting rice fields. They took samples of roots and soils from the infected rice plants and resulted maximum prevalence of *Meloidogyne graminicola* in district Chiniot followed by Faisalabad district of Punjab. They also reported Pakistan as an ancestral area of *Meloidogyne graminicola* and showed greatly different from other isolates due to high variability in the genome and long branch length in Pakistan. They resulted that rice fields are greatly affected by genetically modified *Meloidogyne graminicola* all over the World.

Nahiyoon *et al.* (2019) studied the cotton plant fields and also the attack of parasitic nematodes over these crops. They recorded that after wheat, cotton is widely grown crop in Pakistan. The aimed of the study was that how many cotton crop fields in Sindh, Pakistan are affected due to parasitic nematodes. In this study, they obtained samples of cotton plants roots. They isolated and identified the soil nematodes namely, *Tylenchorhynchus ewingi* and *Acrobeloides gossypii*. Hussain *et al.* (2016) studied the susceptibility of okra plant against *Meloidogyne incognita* infection in green houses. They studied twenty-eight (28) okra cultivars. They resulted *Pusa swami* the most susceptible cultivar to *Meloidogyne incognita*.

Khan *et al.*, (2016) conducted a comprehensive survey to study the occurrence and control of plant parasitic nematodes associated with the pomegranate seedlings in major growing nurseries of Balochistan, Pakistan. They resulted *Helicotylenchus digonicus* the most frequent nematodes observed at all the surveyed nurseries of Balochistan. They also observed the effects of different treatments to control the parasitic nematodes of pomegranate seedlings in Balochistan. Ahmed *et al.* (2015) conducted a survey in major growing six (6) districts of Punjab, Pakistan to assess the nematodes populations. They

reported eight (8) plant parasitic nematode genera and some other soil nematodes by analyzing sixty-nine (69) soil samples taken from rhizosphere areas of different crops. They observed species of *Tylenchorhynchus*, *Xiphinema*, and *Cephalobus* the most abundantly found in all soil samples surveyed. They reported high prevalence of nematodes in Bahauddin and Gujranwala districts of Punjab, Pakistan. Zarina *et al.* (2015) carried out a detailed survey in fifteen (15) chilli growing areas of Sindh to investigate the abundance and diversity of soil and plant parasitic nematodes. They reported fifty-two (52) species with three newly discovered species and thirty-three (33) genera of nematodes, of which Three (3) species were saprophytic, thirty-four (34) were migratory ecto-parasite, one (1) carnivorous, four (4) endo-parasite, eight (8) free living and five (5) were infecting bacteria or fungi. Singh *et al.* (2015) pointed out that plant parasitic nematodes are threat for the agriculture in the whole universe.

Today's, the poverty as well as hunger level in the world is being increasing, which is due to the parasitic nematodes effects on crops. They described in the study that millions dollar loss is occurring each year due to parasitic nematodes attacks. It has been very difficult to reduce their growth while they are also being causing reduction in the growth and even death of other beneficial and attractive microorganisms.

Khan *et al.* (2015) a survey was carried out to investigate the plant parasitic nematodes associated with six (6) almond nurseries in Kalat and Khuzdar districts of province Balochistan. They recorded sixteen (16) different kinds of nematodes of which *Meloidogyne javanica*, *Zygotylenchus guevarai* and *Scutylenchus rugosus* were found to be present in all six (6) almond nurseries. Hussain *et al.* (2015) took a survey of twelve localities of district Layyah of Punjab, Pakistan. They took twenty-four samples of roots and soil. They recorded *Meloidogyne incognita* the most prominent specie in the samples of all location. They also recorded many other species of plant parasitic nematodes like *Criconeema*, *Pratylenchus*, *Aplelenchus*, *Longidorus*, *Helicotylenchus*, *hoploaimus*, *Xiphinema*. Zia *et al.* (2014) conducted a comprehensive survey over majorly growing twenty-three locations of the four (4) tehsils of district Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan, to investigate the root-knot nematodes associated and infected tomato crops. They reported eight-seven (87%) tomato fields infestation by root-knot nematodes. They also reported *Meloidogyne incognita*, the most abundant population found in the surveyed fields of tomatoes in Faisalabad district, Punjab, Pakistan. Asmaa *et al.* (2014) carried out a two-years (2) detailed survey of identification of plant parasitic nematodes associated with different kinds of plants at various regions of Jazan province of Saudi Arabia. They collected

a total of 679 roots and soil samples from the surveyed areas and identified sixteen (16) parasitic nematodes genera while *Meloidogyne* species were the most prevalent with highest occurrence frequency and density. Khan *et al.* (2013) carried out a comprehensive survey of six (6) nurseries of apple in Kalat and Khuzdar districts of Balochistan, Pakistan. They collected sixty (60) soil and root samples from rhizosphere regions of the apple surveyed. They recorded six (6) different plant parasitic nematodes associated with the seedlings of apple surveyed nurseries. They recorded *Xiphinema americanum* the most prominent nematode species and *Tylenchus butteus* species in single locality. Aly khan and Juma khan treen. (2012) isolated and identified nine genera of parasitic nematodes while surveying Cherry (*Prunus avius L*) roots nematodes at six different localities (Surab, Mugalzai, Kalat, Mastung, Quetta and Mangochar) of Balochistan, province of Pakistan. They recorded high frequency of *Helicotylenchus cavenessi* and *Xiphinema rivesi*.

Table No. 1- Showing relevant locality of ten crops cultivated and sampled in district Musakhail Baluchistan.

Common name	No. of plants	Botanical name	Locality sampled
Wheat	5	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Khajori, Dakian, Tangsar, Kiwan, Toi
Mung bean	5	<i>Vigna radiate</i>	Zam, Zimriplasin, Chesenna, Rarahsham, Tangisar.
Corn	5	<i>Zea mays L.</i>	Khajori, Tangsar, Dakian, Kiwan, Toi,
Okra	5	<i>Abelmoscus esculentus</i>	Zimriplasin, Chesenna, Zam, Rarahsham, Tangisar.
Eggplant	10	<i>Solanum melongena L.</i>	Khajori, Zimriplasin, Tangsar, Chesenna, Kiwan Zam, Toi, Dakian, Rarahsham, Tangisar.
Tomato	10	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum L</i>	Khajori, Zimriplasin, Tangsar, Chesenna, Kiwan Zam, Toi, Dakian, Rarahsham, Tangisar.

Pepper	10	<i>Capsicum annum L.</i>	Khajori, Zimriplasin, Tangsar, Chesenna, Kiwan Zam, Toi, Dakian, Rarahsham, Tangisar.
Apple	10	<i>Malus pumila Mill.</i>	Khajori, Zimriplasin, Tangsar, Chesenna, Kiwan Zam, Toi, Dakian, Rarahsham, Tangisar.
Watermelon	5	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	Khajori, Zimriplasin, Tangsar, Chesenna, Kiwan
Grapes	5	<i>Vitis vinifera L.</i>	Zam, Toi, Dakian, Rarahsham, Tangisar

Total no. of plant samples= 70

Table No.2- List of English names, scientific names and family names of the surveyed field crops, vegetables and fruit plants cultivated in district Musakhail.

English names	Scientific names	Family names
Wheat	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	Poaceae
Mung bean	<i>Vigna radiate</i>	Fabaceae
Corn	<i>Zea mays L.</i>	Poaceae
Okra	<i>Abelmoscus esculentus</i>	Malvaceae
Eggplant	<i>Solanum melongena L.</i>	Solanaceae
Tomato	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum L.</i>	Solanaceae
Pepper	<i>Capsicum annum L.</i>	Solanaceae
Apple	<i>Malus pumila Mill</i>	Rosaceae
Watermelon	<i>Citrullus lanatus</i>	Cucurbitaceae

Grapes	<i>Vitis vinifera L</i>	Vitaceae
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Table No.3- Showing presence and absence of plant parasitic nematode genera in different localities of district Musakhail.

Sites	<i>Hetrodera</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i>	<i>Aphelenchus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i>
Tangsar	+	+	-	-	-
Zimriplasin	-	-	-	+	-
Zam	-	-	-	+	-
Toi	-	+	+	-	-
Chesenna	-	+	-	+	+
Dakian	+	+	+	+	-
Tangisar	-	-	-	+	-
Kiwan	-	+	-	-	+
Khajori	-	+	+	-	+
Rarahsham	-	-	+	-	+

Table No.4. Showing Presence and Absence of Nematode Genera in Different Host Plants

Samples	<i>Hetrodera</i>	<i>Meloidogyne</i>	<i>Aphelenchus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i>
Wheat	+	-	-	-	-
Mung bean	-	+	-	+	+
Corn	-	+	+	-	-
Okra	-	-	+	+	+
Eggplant	-	+	+	-	-
Tomato	-	+		-	+

Pepper	-	+	+	+	-
Apple	-	-	-	+	+
Watermelon	-	+	-	+	-
Grapes	-	+	-	-	-

Key words: Presence = + and Absence = -

Table No.5- Showing occurrence frequency of nematodes genera identified Frequency of occurrence % = Number of positive samples / totals collected soil samplesx100

Nematode genera	Occurrence frequency%
<i>Hetrodera</i>	1.42
<i>Meloidogyne</i>	10
<i>Aphelenchus</i>	5.71
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	7.14
<i>Ditylenchus</i>	5.71

Table No.6- Showing population densities of nematodes in 100 gm of soil population densities of nematode genera = No. of nematodes /100 gm soil

Nematode genera	Population densities
<i>Hetrodera</i>	0.01
<i>Meloidogyne</i>	0.07
<i>Aphelenchus</i>	0.04
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	0.05
<i>Ditylenchus</i>	0.04

Table No.7- Showing incidence of nematodes at different sites.

Sites studied	Incidence%
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Tangsar	28.57
Zimriplasin	0
Zam	14.28
Toi	28.57
Chesenna	57.14
Dakian	71.42
Tangisar	14.28
Kiwan	42.85
Khajori	57.14
Rarahsham	42.85

Incidence (%) = Number of infected plant/ Total number of observed plants in the given site \times 100

Conclusion

The soil of district Musakhail is more favorable for phytonematodes development, growth and reproduction. Various types of phytonematodes are associated with different plants. Genera *Meloidogyne* is the most abundant of all the nematodes identified. *Meloidogyne* species are affecting most of the species of plant surveyed in most of the sites. Preventive measures should be taken to control their populations for better and greater yields of field crops, vegetables and fruit plants. It is essential to train farmers with modern technologies of planting healthy seedlings. It is concluded that both organic manures and nematicides may be utilized to manage and eradicate the nematode populations. Organic manures like poultry manures, cow dungs, pigeon manures, goat pellets are more appropriate because these are eco-friendly and possess no toxic effects on physical environment and biotic components as compared to the nematicides. Utilization of organic mucks along with nematicides show best results. The organic dungs improve the development and growth of field crops, vegetables and fruit plants as well as yield production. The organic excrements also prevent the plants from damages.

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